

ENERGETIC COSTS OF RICH REFINERY GASES PROCESSING AND SEPARATION

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Abstract

The Saturated gas plant (SGP) plays an important role in the refinery's light ends part. It is generally accounted to highly energy demanding units. In SLOVNAFT the situation in electric energy consumption is further worsened by the operation of the clearly oversized gases compressor S251. However this fact also results in very small value of marginal electric energy consumption in this unit thus being a suitable example of differences between specific and marginal operational parameters. Application of marginal rather than specific parameters to the refinery production planning and optimization software might lead to better operation optimum and thus to higher refinery profit in the end. Parallel to this issue we also investigated the possibility of limited-scope reconstruction of the currently rarely used smaller gases compressor S51, aimed at sufficient suction capacity increase as to enable its continuous operation and thus achieve substantial electric energy savings compared to S251 operation. The obtained solution showed as too expensive, suffering from the wide gases molar masses range and mass flows. In the end the gases processing in the whole refinery has been reevaluated and there is a new membrane-based gases separation unit under commissioning that, among other benefits, makes the S51 reconstruction unnecessary.

1 Introduction

The saturated gas plant (SGP) is an important production unit in a conventional refinery. It desulphurizes, compresses and separates gases and liquid gases (LPG) from various refinery units (usually referred to as “rich gases” due to increased content of C3 and heavier hydrocarbons) usually into Ethane fraction (EF), propane, C4 fraction (which can further be split into n-C4 and i-C4 streams) and C5+ fraction (containing mostly C5 to C7 hydrocarbons).[1] It thus combines both environmental and economic effects for the refinery by helping to meet the continuously more stringent criteria of sulphur content in refinery products as well as the SO_x emissions limits. The gases separation part might be based, or combine absorption [2], membrane [3] and cryogenic [4] technologies.

In SLOVNAFT refinery the sour and rich gases are collected on two pressure levels: the low pressure one (LP gases, around 0.3 to 0.4 MPa abs) and the elevated one (MP gases, over 0.6 MPa abs). The collected LP gases are desulphurized (removal of H₂S and other sulphides) in the low pressure ammine scrubber (countercurrent multiple stage absorption column) and led to low pressure stage compressor suction at about 0.12 MPa abs. The MP gases are desulphurized in another ammine scrubber and sent to the compressor suction at about 0.5 MPa. After being compressed to about 1.6 MPa abs, the gases are mixed with desulphurized LPG and sent to pentane absorption column which uses the C5 fraction as the pentane solvent. Its overhead

product is the Ethane fraction, rich in hydrogen and is sent to the refinery's fuel gas network. Its bottom product is sent to pentane regenerator, yet another column, that yields the C3C4 fraction as the overhead product and regenerated C5 fraction as the bottom one. Part of the C5 fractions is led to storage and the rest returns to the pentane absorber. C3C4 fraction in the end is split into C3 and C4 fraction in the depropanizer rectification column and those fractions are separately sent into storage. In the contrast to a standard SGP design [2], the SGP in SLOVNAFT lacks the gasoline recovery and redistillation part as the light and heavy gasolines are already separated in the preceding units.

The saturated ammine solvent from the ammine scrubbers is sent to ammine regeneration column, which is a multiple stage desorption column, where the H₂S-rich overhead gases are sent to Sulphur recovery unit and the regenerated solvent is used in ammine scrubbers again. The ammine regenerator is reboiled by condensing low pressure steam (0.5 MPa abs); the pentane absorber, desorber and the depropanizer are reboiled by condensing middle pressure steam (1.1 to 1.2 MPa abs).

The SGP is equipped with two compressors, S51 and S251, both driven by electromotors. The smaller one, S51 has insufficient compression capacity in most cases and is thus in operation just during regular refinery units revisions (mostly 1 to 2 months per 1 to 2 years). The bigger S251 compressor is thus in nearly permanent operation. When in operation, the S51 consumes 0.9 to 1.1 MW electricity and reaches the discharge pressure of maximum 1.2 MPa abs, whereas the S251 operates with nearly constant load of 1.9 to 2.1 MW and is able to reach the discharge pressure of 1.6 MPa abs.

Such SGP operational state reflects the structural changes the refinery underwent in the last 20 years. Compared to the past, the obtained desulphurized gases contain more hydrogen and less C₃ and higher hydrocarbons. This is the result of new hydrocracking and hydrotreating units commissioned in the late 1990s, that increased the amount of light gases to be desulphurized and separated containing even over 40 % vol. hydrogen, but the major part of C₃ and higher hydrocarbons nowadays is separated in preceding unit and routed to the SGP in liquid form.

Due to the high electric energy and (more than 0.12 MWh per t of processed gas) and the high amount of water steam consumed (appr. 1 t per t of processed gases) the SGP is considered as a very energy – intense unit and several attempts have been made in the past to reduce the amount of consumed energy media. One of them led in the year 2009 to the shutdown of the heptane absorption – desorption loop, where the C₂ fraction from the pentane absorber has been purified from the entrained evaporated pentane solvent. Other ideas dealt with separation of the lightest gases from the LP and MP gases and their direct routing to the refinery's fuel gas network. However in all cases the obtainable energy savings were outweighed by the associated C₃+ hydrocarbons loss, as their material value is higher than that as gaseous fuel for the furnaces and boilers in the refinery.

2 Aims of the contribution

As already briefly addressed above, the SGP is considered among the most energy demanding units in the refinery, expressed in terms of specific energy consumption. This also is reflected in the specific energy consumption values implemented in the refinery production planning and optimization software. In cooperation with the responsible Supply chain management department we developed an alternative way of energy consumption evaluation and forecasting, that both manages to describe the load dependence of energies consumption far better than the currently used specific energy consumption parameter and most importantly is readily applicable into the software.

We chose the SGP as a very suitable example for the methodic demonstration and explanation of the observed differences between the specific energies consumptions and the newly obtained marginal ones. In nearly all production units cases we have obtained smaller marginal than

specific parameters, meaning that the planning and optimization software generally assigns greater variable feed processing costs to them at the moment than are the true variable costs represented by marginal parameters. This could lead to such situation, that the optimum found by the software differs from the objective optimum and leads to lower refinery profit in the end. Furthermore we provide a concise overview addressing the proposed S51 compressor reconstruction idea aimed at increasing its suction capacity, the related problems we encountered and outcome of this activity.

3 Applied methodic

The Operative production scheduling department provided us with balanced data about the SGP load and energies consumption in the form of daily averages in one year duration. We filtered the data to remove transient states (SGP starts and shutdowns) and the rest of data were subjected to linear analysis. Thus, instead of the currently used $y = kx$ relation between a particular energy consumption y and the units load x , with k being the specific energy consumption, we described the data with linear fit in the form of $y = px + q$ where the meaning of y and x is the same, p represents the marginal energy consumption and q the fix energy consumption value.

As for the S51 reconstruction idea, we analyzed historic values of mass flows of compressed gases, their molar mass as well as the design parameters of both S51 and S251 compressors. In cooperation with their manufacturer – ČKD – we tried to find the optimum reconstruction configuration that would avoid a complex compressor reconstruction: the compressor skid and the electromotor had to remain the same. In addition, the increased compressor suction capacity should enable continuous compressor operation within the usual range of gases molar masses and even during summer, when the gases mass and volumetric flows are usually the highest.

4 Obtained results and their analysis

Results of historical SGP operational data analysis are shown in Fig 1. In this figure we see clear discrepancies between the specific and marginal energy consumption parameters, the most visible being those in electric energy and low pressure steam consumption.

In order to explain these differences, one must firstly understand how the specific energy consumption is calculated: The total electric energy consumption in a certain period (the whole previous year or a shorter period of characteristic stable units operation due to the decision of the responsible unit technologists) is divided by the total amount of feed (processed gases) in the same period. Thus this value represents the specific weighed average of certain energy consumption in a particular production unit in the past year that is calculated anew each year and is applied to the refinery's operation planning and optimization software. If the next year's load is not to differ much from the previous year's one and there are no major technology changes, the calculation model yields quite realistic total energy consumption prediction. Such approach thus leads in the majority of cases to total energy consumption results that do not differ too much from reality and is therefore still applied till today. As can be seen in the given figure, despite yielding reasonable total energy consumption predictions, the existing model utterly fails to describe the energy consumption load dependence. This drawback is removed by our approach.

A deeper insight into technologic processes provides explanation for quite small (nearly zero) values of marginal electric energy and low pressure steam consumption: the compressor S251 (S51) stands for the major share of total electric energy consumption in the SGP. As mentioned above, the S251 compressor load is nearly independent as it constantly operates with active antisurge control: thus its load varies only slightly. The low pressure steam consumption is closely related to the mass flow on ammine used in the ammine scrubbers. Due to issues related to columns hydrodynamics, their desulphurization efficiency and maximum allowable ammine

H₂S load, the ammine mass flow varies only slightly with desulphurized gases mass flow as thus also does the low pressure steam consumption. The middle pressure steam consumption is closely related to the mass flow of processed gases thus its specific and marginal consumption do not differ much.

Fig. 1 Most important energies consumption load dependence for the SGP

We can conclude this part with the key finding, that most refining and petrochemical units in SLOVNAFT refinery exhibit similar energy consumption load dependence behavior to that of SGP. The correct assessment of this finding could enable the refinery to improve its planning and optimization process and thereby to reach higher profit in the end.

Parallel to this analysis, we examined the possibility of the smaller S51 compressor reconstruction in order to increase its low pressure stage suction capacity sufficiently to enable its continuous operation in common SGP operational states. As is presented in Tab. 2, while its

low pressure stage mass flow capacity would nearly suffice for current LP gases, it frequently does not meet the required volumetric capacity due to often lower than designed LP gases molar mass.

Fig. 2a documents current 1st and 2nd compressor stage suction molar masses in the range in the range of 30 to 45 kg/kmol. In coordination with ČKD, based on usual gases mass flows and molar masses we set the desired low pressure stage suction capacity to 11 t/h; with the gases molar mass range of 33 to 39 kg/kmol. It is its maximum suction capacity that can be achieved within proposed compressor reconstruction scope at the same time.

Tab. 1 Design and real operational parameters of gases compression in the SGP

Operational parameter	S251 design	S51 design	Real SGP operation	Desired S51 parameters after reconstruction
Low pressure stage suction capacity, t/h	16	10	5 to 10 (fresh LP gas flow)	Min. 11
High pressure stage suction capacity, t/h	36	22	8 to 14 (fresh LP+MP gas flow)	Max. 20
Gases molar mass M, kg/kmol	35 to 45	39 to 45	30 to 45 (50)	33 to 39
Discharge pressure, MPa abs.	1.6	1.6	1.5 to 1.6 (S251) 1 to 1.2 (S51)	Min. 1.4 (low M) to 1.8

Fig. 2 a-d Graphical overview of calculation results. **a:** Molar mass of LP and MP gases before and after their adjustment; **b:** Mass flows of gases on both compressor stages suctions before and after their M adjustment; **c:** Mass flows of EF used for M adjustment; **d:** Gases exceeding compressor suction capacity sent to refinery's fuel gas network

Having defined the limits of possible S51 low pressure stage suction capacity, we still had to deal with the problem of wide gases molar mass ranges. While those below 33 kg/kmol occur quite rarely, those above 39 kg/kmol are encountered quite often. However if a continuous gases

composition analyzer is installed at both compression stage suctions, this problem can be overcome by regulated EF recirculation to compressor suction (molar mass 15 to 19 kg/kmol). The Figure 2a compares the original and the by EF recirculation adjusted LP and MP gases molar masses. Figure 2b documents that the low pressure stage suction capacity of 11 t/h suffices for most of the time even with adjusted LP gases molar mass, whereas in the second stage still exists free suction capacity. As appears from the Figure 2c, the recirculated EF mass flow lies usually below 1 t/h to both compression stages suction together (cca. 5000 t/year). Unfortunately in certain situations the 1st compression stage suction capacity does not suffice and a part of the LP (or even more rarely MP) gases has to be sent to refinery's fuel gas network via the gases recompression station. (cca. 150 t/year).

The EF recirculation causes certain increase in 1.1 MPa steam consumption in the SGP, as it makes the pentane solvent mass flow increase necessary. Also the gases sent to fuel gas network have impact on the resulting economic balance, presented in Tab 2.

Tab 2 Approximate S51 reconstruction economic balance

Electricity savings, mil. €/year	Extra consumed steam costs, mil. €/year	Gases sent to recompression station, mil. €/year	Net savings, mil. €/year	Reconstruction costs estimation by ČKD, mil. €	Simple pay back period, years
0.52	-0.1	- 0.05	0.37	2	5.4

As appears from that table the S51 reconstruction is less attractive than expected, mainly due to estimated reconstruction costs. The cost estimation is still incomplete, as the continuous gases analyzers (chromatographs) together with the needed extra regulation for EF recirculation would certainly increase it further. Thus the S51 reconstruction idea has been rejected in the end. Another working team later more successfully dealt with gases processing in the refinery in a more complex way: as a result a new membrane unit is to be put into operation in 2017. It makes the S51 reconstruction unnecessary.

5 Conclusions

In this study we demonstrated the need to evaluate the true variable energetic costs properly in industrial processes in form of marginal costs. The SGP appears as a very suitable demonstration example as it ranks among the most energy intense units in the refinery and at the same time it exhibits almost zero electric energy and low pressure steam marginal costs.

In the second part of it we presented the results of possible S51 compressor reconstruction examination that sought to put this smaller compressor into continuous operation with the larger S251 serving as stand by, thus saving several hundreds of kW of electricity. The variable LP and MP gases mass flows and molar masses made the procedure quite difficult despite very intense cooperation with the compressors manufacturer. The resulting (theoretically) suitable solution to those issues; was too costly and made the whole reconstruction economically unattractive. Nowadays a new gases separation membrane unit is under construction that is to enable continuous S51 operation even without reconstruction.

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References

- [1] SGP unit operation manual.
- [2] Gary, J. H., Handwerk, G. E., Kaiser, M. J.: Petroleum refining technology and economics, Fifth edition, ISBN 978-0-203-90792-4, Taylor & Francis Group 2007, page 279.
- [3] Baker, R. W.: Membranes for vapor/gas separation. Available online at: http://www.mtrinc.com/publications/MT01%20Fane%20Memb%20for%20VaporGas_Sep%202006%20Book%20Ch.pdf.
- [4] Encyclopedia of Chemical Processing and Design, Volume 28 by McKetta Jr, J. J., ISBN 0-8247-2451-8, CRC Press 1988, page 232.